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USING DEDUCTIVE AND INDUCTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to the problems of using deductive and inductive ways of teaching during lessons. Here, I try to show advantages and disadvantages of these two methods and which method is more effective and fruitful in English classes.*

Key words: *deductive and inductive approach, time-saving, discover rules, motivated, critical thinking, making-up dialogue, making a little story, role-play, cards*

Deductive teaching is a traditional approach in which information about target language and rules are driven at the beginning of the class and continued with examples [1]. In the beginning of the lesson may be boring for learners. Younger learners may not be able to understand the concepts or encounter grammar terminology given. Because it's a teacher-centered method, learners are less involved. But this method can be time-saving. After explanation, students do exercises. Rules and aspects can be more simply and clearly explained than elicited from examples.

Deductive method confirms many learners expectations about classroom learning, particularly for those who have an analytical style [3].

Thornbury notes that in an inductive approach learners are provided with samples which include the target grammar that they will learn. Then students work on the examples and try to discover the rules themselves. When students obtain the grammar rules and they practice the language by creating their own examples [2].

Teaching by separating students to groups in order to work collaboratively is difficult. Although it takes more time and energy-consuming, It appeals to students to participate actively in whole lesson. This method encourages the teacher to design data or materials taught carefully and systematically. In these activities, they will be motivated.

The main difference between inductive and deductive approaches to research is that whilst a deductive approach is aimed and testing theory, an inductive approach is concerned with the generation of new theory emerging from data.

As is state above, deductive method is to do tasks by using theory. Inductive method is to discover rule by using their own examples.

As you see, both methods have their own features. To my mind, inductive method is more efficient and interesting in English classes. Because, the students are more actively involved in the learning process rather than passive recipients. This method

makes learners guess be attentive listening and learning and enhance learning autonomy which is very crucial in developing skills and abilities. Every teacher wants to teach learners in an efficient way. They regularly look for effective and fruitful ways to increase students' interests during the lessons. Every lesson should motivate students to gain wide range of knowledge. Using inductive method develops students' critical thinking ability. It includes some interesting and motivating activities, such as making-up dialogues, round-table discussions, role-play, working with pictures, labeling activities. For example, If a theme has a lot of new words, idioms and phrases, a teacher can use **making-up dialogue** or **making a little story** or **role-play** by using the new words. If they make up their own sentences, students comprehend on what conditions they can use the words and idioms. **Using cards** is efficient in teaching vocabulary lessons and consolidate their knowledge, especially, all previous lessons. In this task, a teacher gives the cards to the students in which at least two answers are written. Then, a teacher gives a question. If who has a correct answer in their card, they have to raise their hands. In this case, more than one students may raise their hands. The teacher have them tell their answers. Then, the teacher put "+" sign who tells a correct answer and put "-" sign who tells wrong answer. If there is no correct answer, the teacher put "-" sign who doesn't tell the answer despite the fact that the answer was written in his or her card. We can use this activity in grammar lesson to consolidate tenses. For example, the teacher gives a question: "Which tense do we use to tell general truth?". The student in whose card was written present simple should raise their hand. In the end the teacher should count the number of "+" and can know who reached high point. It is very interesting and motivating activity which involve all students in one activity. It encourages students to be very attentive in every question and it also helps the teacher to assess students' individual knowledge. In inductive method teacher can create a communicational environment with learners. Learners can share their ideas, opinions freely. If teachers use different materials, up-to-date technologies during the lessons, they can increase the students' interests to the lessons.

To sum it up, a teacher must be aware of all advantages and disadvantages in using all types of methodologies. There is no best or worst method. The main factor in the choice of methods is the learners' need and character. A teacher must be a good pedagogue to see and understand all the students' individual abilities. Understanding the students helps us to choose the efficient way of teaching.

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